

IMPROVING THE PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE OF FUTURE TEACHERS ON THE BASIS OF A CONTEXTUAL APPROACH IN LEARNING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE.

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Abstract: Contextual approach is very important in learning a foreign language. This article analyzes the theoretical foundations of the contextual approach to language learning, its advantages and effectiveness. The contextual approach helps to learn the language based on real-life situations and conversations during the language learning process. This method increases students' communicative competence and develops their skills of practical language use. The article helps to create a complete picture of the uniqueness of the contextual approach to learning a foreign language and its role in the educational process.

Keywords: foreign language learning, contextual approach, communicative competence, language learning methods, real life situations, communication, practical application, language education, linguistics

As a result of the reforms aimed at ensuring the development of modern approaches in the professional education system, which includes the continuous education system based on advanced foreign experiences, modernizing the content of the training of future specialists, students' work opportunities Research is being conducted on the creation of an educational environment aimed at creating the necessary conditions that allow for the realization. The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-60 on the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for the years 2022-2026, the Concept of the Development of the Higher Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030 is the program of our research work. Systematic reforms are being carried out in our country regarding the organization and development of vocational education , is interpreted as a specific form of the individual's social competence arising on the basis of acquisition of skills. Professional training does not occur by itself, but covers specific stages in the process of learning a foreign

language different approaches and methods are used. In recent years, the contextual approach has gained great importance in language education. This approach increases students' ability to use the language in real-life situations and communication. This article analyzes the main principles, advantages and effectiveness of the contextual approach in learning a foreign language.

Theoretical foundations of the contextual approach. In addition, the concept of competence is also important in the characteristics of the development of professional competence in future pedagogues. Competence - requires constant enrichment of one's knowledge and skills, learning new information, feeling the demands of the current era, the ability to find new knowledge, process it and apply it during one's work. According to these theories, language learning takes place through social interaction and the meaning of language is determined through its context.

Advantages:

1. Communicative competence: A contextual approach develops students' skills in practical language use. Through this method, students are prepared to communicate in real life situations.

2. Understanding the meaning: Through the context, the meaning of words and phrases is more clearly understood.

3. Memory and consolidation: Language materials learned using a contextual approach are meaningful and interesting for students, and are retained in their memory longer. Words and phrases used in real-life situations are better remembered.

According to international experience, the professional competency of educators, including the development of the most optimal methods of implementation (multi-level interactive education), effective models, the organization of an innovative educational environment, and the improvement of methodological support for the implementation of the educational process there is a need. This aspect requires the development of professional competence of middle level specialists in vocational education. Modernization of educational forms and methods in the organization of the educational process, development of methods and scientific bases of formation of professional competence, as well as development of a modern methodical system of formation of professional competence of middle level specialists in vocational education and its implementation there is a need to determine the editorial conditions of the increase, to improve the content of the educational materials. Based

on this necessity, it is necessary to introduce development technologies based on the comprehensive approach, to develop teaching methods and didactic tools for professional subjects. It is not justified to implement a competency-based approach, based on international experience, neglecting the achievements of local pedagogy and psychology.

The role of the contextual approach in the educational process

1. Creating a language environment: By placing students in a language environment, their natural communication skills develop. This is done by conducting practical exercises based on different situations and roles in language classes.

2. Interactive and discussion-based lessons: Students are encouraged to actively communicate with each other. Through group activities, discussions, role plays and simulations, students will have the opportunity to apply their knowledge and skills in practice.

3. Use of real materials: The use of real-life materials such as texts, videos, audio materials makes the language learning process more meaningful. It prepares students to use the language in real-life situations.

4. Integrated learning: The contextual approach can be integrated with other disciplines. For example, learning a language based on situations related to history, geography, art and culture expands students' knowledge and arouses their interest in various fields.

SUMMARY

Contextual approach is very important in learning a foreign language. This approach develops students' language communication skills in real-life situations and increases their communicative competence. The knowledge learned through the contextual approach is meaningful and interesting for students, and is retained in their memory longer. Also, this approach helps to understand the cultural context and makes the learning process interesting and motivating. Therefore, the use of a contextual approach in foreign language education is an effective and useful method.

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